

Role of Nanoparticles in Drug Delivery System

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Abstract

Nanomedicine and nano delivery systems are new but rapidly developing science which serve as means of diagnostic tools or to deliver therapeutic agents to specific targeted sites in a controlled manner. Novel drug delivery systems have several advantages over conventional multi dose therapy. Drug designing at the nanoscale has been of its potential advantages such as the possibility to modify properties like solubility, drug release profiles, diffusivity, bioavailability and immunogenicity. Nanoparticles can offer significant advantages in terms of high stability, high specificity, high drug carrying capacity, ability for controlled release, possibility to use in different route of administration and the capability to deliver both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drug molecules and include the mechanism of increased penetration and retention, the transport of insoluble drugs and the controlled release. Nanoparticles vary in size but are generally ranging from 1 to 100 nm. The intent is to highlight the potential of nanoparticle formulation, characterization, mechanism of nano particles, potential role of nanoparticle in livestock and advantages of nanoparticles in delivery of drug molecules.

Introduction

Nanotechnology refers to the manipulation of the structure of materials, substances, or elements at the nanometer scale, producing structures between 1.0 nm and 100 nm. Nanomedicine is a relatively new discipline that arises from the intersection between nanotechnology and medicine. The use of materials in this range has been a great advance for the pharmacology by modifying fundamental properties of the drugs such as solubility, diffusivity, half-life in the bloodstream and drug release and distribution profiles. Nanotechnology is shown to bridge the barrier of biological and physical sciences by applying nanostructures and nanophases at various fields of science

especially in nanomedicine and nano based drug delivery systems, where such particles are of major interest (Severino *et al.*, 2020)

Delivering therapeutic compound to the desirable site is a major problem in treatment of many diseases. Conventional utilization of drugs is characterized by poor bio distribution, limited effectiveness, undesirable side effects, and lack of selectivity. Nanotechnology and Nanoscience studies have emerged rapidly during the past years in a broad range of product domains. Nanotechnology employs curative agents at the nanoscale level to develop nanomedicines. The field of biomedicine comprising nanobiotechnology, drug delivery, biosensors and tissue engineering has been powered by nanoparticles. Nanomedicines have become well appreciated in recent times due to the fact that nanostructures could be utilized as delivery agents by encapsulating drugs or attaching therapeutic drugs and deliver them to target tissues more precisely with a controlled release. This targeted and sustained drug delivery decreases the drug related toxicity and increase patient's compliance with less frequent dosing. Nanotechnology has proven beneficial in the treatment of cancer, AIDS and many other diseases, in veterinary medicine, also providing advancement in diagnostic testing (Karuppusamy and Venkatesan 2017).

Characteristics of Nanoparticle

Nanoparticles can enter the human body, via three main route, direct injection, inhalation and oral intake. Once, they enter systemic circulation, first phenomenon taking place before distribution into various organs is particle-protein interaction. Absorption from the blood capillaries allows the lymphatic system to further distribute and eliminate the particles. This system has three main functions, two of which pertain to drug delivery which are fluid recovery & encompasses immunity.

Size of particle

The shape and size of nanoparticles is important because on its shape and size it dictate their distribution, toxicity, and targeting ability. Nanoparticles can cross the Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB) providing sustained delivery of medication for diseases that were previously difficult to treat. As particles size get smaller, their surface area to volume ratio gets larger. This would imply that more of the drug is closer to the surface of the particle compared to a larger molecule. Being at or near the surface would lead to faster drug release. It would be beneficial to create nanoparticle systems that have a large surface area to volume ratio thus particle could pass through the Blood-brain barrier (BBB), sufficient amount of drug delivery due to high surface area to volume ratio, and avoiding immediate clearance by the lymphatic system (Sajid and Płotka-Wasyłka, 2020).

Surface properties

Manipulation of surface characteristics is important to generate the ideal system. To an optimum nanoparticle drug delivery system, the incorporation of appropriate targeting ligands, surface curvature and reactivity is important to address the prevention of aggregation, stability, and receptor binding and subsequent pharmacological effects of the drug. The more hydrophobic a nanoparticle is, the more likely it is to be cleared due to higher binding of blood components. Making nanoparticles surface hydrophilic would increase their time in circulation. In fact, coating the nanoparticles with polymers or surfactants or creating copolymers has been proven valuable. Copolymer nanoparticles are often referred as “stealth” nanoparticles, because without opsonisation, they remain undetected by the reticuloendothelial system (RES). By creating polymer complexes, clearance issues have been solved but aggregation is still a drawback with small particles due to large surface area. Particularly, nanoparticles such as dendrimers, quantum dots, and micelles are especially prone to aggregation (Mohanraj and Chen, 2006)

Drug loading

The drug loading of the nanoparticles is generally defined as the amount of drug bound per mass of polymer (usually moles of drug per mg polymer or mg drug per mg polymer); it could also be given as percentage relative to the polymer. The technique used for this analysis is classical analytical methods like UV spectroscopy or high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) after ultracentrifugation, ultrafiltration, gel filtration, or centrifugal ultrafiltration. Quantification is performed with the UV spectroscopy or HPLC.

Drug release

Drug release assays are also similar to drug loading assay which is assessed for a period of time to analyse the mechanism of drug release.

Mechanism Of Action

The passage of nanoparticles to specific locations occurs (Attia *et al.*, 2019)

- 1) Passively
 - 2) Actively through vectorization.
- The passive form is supported by the intrinsic properties of the nanostructured molecule and occurs through the retention and increased permeability effect. This is based on the ability of the nanoparticles to spill blood vessels to other tissues, resulting in accumulation at sites of increased vascular permeability (tumors, infections, and inflammatory areas).

- In active vectorization, the mechanism of action is due to the coupling of a targeting portion. These include specific binders for molecular recognition, monoclonal antibodies, transferrin, peptides, or portions of sugars that lead drugs to the site of action.

Biopolymeric Nanoparticles Used in Drug Delivery System

- Chitosan
- Alginate
- Xanthan gum
- Cellulose
- Liposomes
- Polymeric micelles
- Dendrimers
- Inorganic nanoparticles
- Nanocrystals
- Metallic nanoparticles
- Quantum dots
- Protein and polysaccharides nanoparticle (Pathak *et al.*, 2022)

Potential Uses of Nanotechnology

1. Veterinary medicine: - Nanotechnology has a significant effect for veterinary prescription in numerous fields incorporates therapeutics, diagnostics, tissue building, immunization generation and disinfectants. The normal use of antibiotics in animal production can leave a residue that affects the final consumer whilst even as using nanotechnology reduces the range of antibiotics used because of their Nano size (Youssef *et al.*, 2019).

2. Animal reproduction: - Nanotechnology is an important tool that could benefit the livestock industry, particularly through post-collection manipulation of semen, routinely used for artificial insemination. In reproductive biology, nanoparticles have been reported to increase the longevity of spermatozoa, improve male fertility and select the best spermatozoa for insemination and semen purification. Nanoparticles have been reported detecting oestrus by close infrared fluorescence (El-Sayed and Kamel 2020).

3. Animal health and nutrition: - Nano zinc oxide is considered one of the promising Nano minerals that used to improve the growth rate, immune response and also disorders affect livestock

reproduction. Nano minerals are inexpensive, utilized in lower quantities and act as growth-promoting and immune-stimulating agents so, produce many benefits for animal feed production.

4. Breeding and reproduction: - Diagnosis and treatment of reproductive problems, oestrus detection, sperm freezing and the direct calving interference are done by several nanotechnology applications. Nano sensors are another device with a cell probe. These probes are mainly utilized in diagnoses of genital tract infectious illnesses, metabolic and hormonal issues or may be the detection of oestrus (Hashem. and Gonzalez-Bulnes, 2021).

5. Vaccine: - The immunostimulatory activity of nanoscale materials has been attributed to antigen presentation at the depot effect, stability, conformational integrity, slow release and prolonged exposure to antigens. Additional mechanisms are associated with enhancement of the innate immune response and release of soluble mediators (cytokines, chemokines, and immunomodulatory molecules) that regulate the immune response (Liu *et al.*, 2016).

Applications of Nanoparticles in Drug Delivery System

• Cancer treatments (Tumor targeting)

Cancer is a very complicated biological phenomenon, and can be considered a disease of many diseases. Current chemotherapy is mainly aimed at destroying all rapidly dividing cells. The development of nanoparticles has provided a new avenue for chemotherapy. Micelles and liposomes offer another option for delivery of chemotherapeutic agents. Micelles are great way to make insoluble drugs soluble due to their hydrophobic core and hydrophilic shell, it increases the ability of the nanocarriers to get through fenestrated vasculature of tumors and inflamed tissue through passive transport, thus resulting in higher drug concentration in tumours (Yao *et al.*, 2020)

Carbon nanotubes have very hydrophobic hollow interior, water insoluble drugs can easily be loaded them. The large surface area allows for outer surface functionalization and can be done specifically for a particular cancer receptor as well as contrast agents.

• Diagnostic testing

Current technology for diagnostic testing is hindered by the inadequacies of fluorescent markers including fading of fluorescence after single use, color matching and restricted use of dyes due to a bleeding effect. One important breakthrough was the discovery of quantum dots which can be custom-made in many sharply defined colors. Their absorption spectrum ranges from UV to a wavelength within visible spectrum and provide high quantum yield, tunable emission spectrum and

photostability. Size of the nanodot determines where in the spectra that individual particle falls. Larger particles have longer wavelengths and emission is narrow (Rizvi *et al.*, 2018)

• **HIV and AIDS treatment**

There have been advancements in therapeutics even more effective by creating polymeric nanoparticles that deliver antiretroviral (ARV) drugs intracellularly as well as to the brain. This technology can also be used in adjunct with vaccinations to prevent HIV infections. Nanotechnology has played a pivotal role in delivering the antiretroviral drugs and improving compliance (Liu *et al.*, 2016).

• **Alternative drug and vaccine delivery mechanisms**

At present, there is considerable excitement within the nanotechnology field with regard to the potential use of nano systems as carriers for mucosal vaccine delivery. Many diseases, such as influenza, respiratory syncytial virus infection, measles and meningitis, are associated with the entry of microorganisms across the respiratory mucosal surfaces. This can be accomplished by the delivery of vaccines by the nasal route. Chitosan nanoparticles are mainly used as vaccine carriers for nasal administration because chitosan nanoparticles elicited long-lasting immune responses significantly higher than those of control solutions (Mohammed *et al.*, 2017).

• **Sunscreens / cosmetics**

Nanoparticle have been identified as a potential next generation cosmetic delivery agent that can provide enhanced skin hydration, bioavailability, stability of the agent and controlled occlusion. For example, in sunscreen UV filters, such as titanium dioxide and zinc oxide are used in nano form rather than bulk form to make the sunscreen transparent rather than white. It is also claimed that they are more effective when used in nano form (Onoue *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

The pharmaceutical sciences have been using nanoparticles to reduce toxicity and side effects of drugs. The use of Nanotechnology in medicine and more specifically drug delivery is set to spread rapidly. Nanotechnology is an important tool that could benefit the livestock in veterinary medicine's management of reproduction and breeding and is considered one of the promising Nano minerals that used to improve the growth rate, immune response and also disorders affect livestock reproduction. Ultimately, through the manipulation of molecular size and surface properties, researchers are able to deliver drugs for longer period of time with less frequent dosing (sustained release) and with greater precision and penetration in difficult to access tissues.

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